

Consumers' Responsiveness toward Marketing Mix of Super Stores in Bangladesh: A Case study on Meena Bazaar

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Abstract: *This paper investigates the factors that are responsible in determining the marketing activities of super stores in Bangladesh. By investigating the marketing activities of one of the fast growing super shops, it addresses the preference of consumers as well as the service of them. The research focuses on product's quality, distribution channels, pricing, promotional activities and customer opinion regarding "Meena Bazaar" in Dhaka City. The study reveals that Meena Bazaar promotes their products at premium price in order to maintain quality and their promotional programs have significant influence toward consumers' response. The findings of this study suggest that Meena bazaar should try to hold this performance level and take more large scale promotional efforts which will help them to achieve leadership position among the superstores in Bangladesh.*

Key words: *Consumer response, Superstore, Marketing mix*

1. Introduction:

The lifestyle, preference and demands of consumers are changing rapidly. Superstore culture is playing a vital role in the ever changing purchasing pattern of consumers. With the current shopping practice, superstore has become a necessity by offering unique shopping experience. Superstores have successfully made a breakthrough in the urban lifestyle with the idea of "all essential elements under one roof". Superstore is a one floor large area consisting of the daily goods. Superstores have attempted the massive expansion drive to attract the consumers in terms of status and convenience. A rise in a good number of organized retailing superstores, offer the consumers hygienic items at a competitive price. The expansion of superstores will diversify the choices of consumers and boost their spending pattern. Superstores made debut, successfully attracting consumers, a section of consumers who are successfully turning to chain stores from the soggy market. Dhaka based *Agora* now runs 4 outlets, *Meenabazar* 13, *Prince bazaar* 2, *Nandan* 5 respectively and *Swapno* runs 70 outlets including 30 outside the capital.

Bangladesh Rifles also runs 11 stores in the capital. More than 600 retail outlets are expected to be set up in the next five years in an attempt to attract more consumers. The expansion of outlets will boost consumer's confidence and help to create a market for manufacturers. In the early days of business around 500 consumers would visit a super

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store outlet daily. But now more than ten times, consumers are coming to an outlet everyday.

Meena Bazaar, the new face of superstore in Bangladesh, has opened their first outlet in 2002. Here the combination of quality and price under various brand names offers value to the consumers for their money. Gemcon Food & Agriculture Products Ltd. produces a variety of food items, including organic products, prepared foods and herbal products which are sold through Meena Bazaar retail outlet. Meena Bazaar has thirteen branches, including Khulna and Chittagong. Meena Bazaar occupies a large floor space on a single level and is situated near residential areas in Dhaka city in order to be convenient to consumers. Its basic appeal is the availability of a broad assortment of goods under a single roof at a moderate price. It is now a part of a chain that owns or controls other super stores located in Dhaka. To maintain a profit, Meena bazaar attempts to make up for the low margins with a high sales volume. Moreover it also sells higher margin items. The overall environment for Meena Bazaar and its competitors are changing from a product oriented atmosphere to customer oriented atmosphere where emphasis is put on satisfying all of the consumers' needs. In order to remain competitive, Meena Bazaar wants to re-evaluate its future opportunities for growth without compromising its profits. This study determines consumers' responsiveness toward marketing mix of superstores in Bangladesh. The study was done on Meena bazaar which is one of the famous and large superstore (in terms of outlet) in Bangladesh

2. Literature Review

To understand the responses of consumers toward marketing activities, consumers buying decision is the central point of the marketer's effort. Consumer behavior is complex and ever changing. What a customer buys is not good enough, the reasons of buying are more important. According to Kristen Ducatte (August 2009) to build a successful guideline for increasing sales and promoting positive customer relationships, the marketers must analyze why customers buy and the factors which motivate them to buy.

Rath, Bay, Petrizzi & Gill (2008) opined that consumer behavior is ultimately a study of consumption, which is the use of a resource, product, or service? Best et al.(2004) define consumer behavior is essentially a study of the individuals, groups, and organizations and the processes they use to buy, pay for, and use products and services that satisfy their needs and wants. Solomon & Rabolt, (2004) said this field of study is ongoing and ever changing; consumer behavior is more than just the exchange of money for products. It is important to understand that consumer behavior is not black and white, but complex and multidimensional.

For the purpose of this research, authors want to know how consumers' behavior responses to various marketing efforts used by the marketers of super shop and which stimuli are changed into responses as satisfaction and dissatisfaction. Therefore, what factors derive the differences in consumer's attitudes and how they shape consumer's experience in the market place represent an important subject of investigation.

According to Treise, for successful marketing operations, it is vital fact to understand consumers' attitudes towards various marketing activities. Nwachukwu et al; Webster (1991) opines that consumers attitudes extensively influence their behavioral response to

marketing activities. So, in protecting consumers' interests, understanding of consumers' attitudes toward marketing should aid in devising effective strategies as well as developing regulations by Government agencies.

In general, researchers have focused on a central issue- what causes the differences in consumers' attitudes toward various marketing practices including product quality, pricing, advertising and retailing or selling. Several researches investigated a number of other factors that may influence consumer's attitudes toward marketing.

Marketing mix is one of the major concepts of modern marketing. It is a set of marketing tools that are blended to produce the response the organizations want from the target market. It consists of product, price, place and promotion. According to Kotler & Amstrong (1989) influencing factors for purchasing behavior are marketing mix & personal characteristics. Gupta (1988) indicates marketing mix has a strong relationship with consumers buying patterns, brand choices and incidences of purchase. According to Nilson ; Kotler& Amstrong, many consumers use price as an indication of the quality of the brand which is an important factor in purchasing decision. Place or the distribution channel is a combination of institutions through, which a seller markets product to user or ultimate consumer (Peter & Donnelly, 1992). Different kinds of promotional activities are essential in modern marketing to keep and grow the market share. (McCarthy and Pereault, 1984). Successful sales promotion has to be consistent with the brand values and be consistent with all other aspects of the brand (Peter and Olson, 1990 and Nilson, 1998).

Most of the studies have shown that the factors of marketing mix have a relationship on the purchasing behavior of the consumer. To attain the consumers mind share, the proper arrangement of the marketing mix is essential. Hossein Nezakati, Chin Sock Khim, and Omid Asgari choose product, price, place, promotion, demography of consumer as the determinants of working women's cloth purchasing in Malayshia evidence. Decisions-making determinants in working women's cloth purchasing- Malayshia, evidence by Narges Asgharpour, Amir Emami and Rasol Shafievoun prefer product, price, place and promotion to identify the effect of marketing mix on brand equity. Gihan Wijesundera, Ruwan Abeysekera carried out a research on the factors influencing the demand of beauty soap among female consumers in the greater Colombo region. Results indicate that; price, place, promotion product and some demographic factors influences the demand of beauty soap among female consumers.

Kristen Ducatte (2009) conducted a research on "Primary factors in consumers purchase decisions of women footwear". They found some factors that affect the attitude of consumer while purchasing foot wears. They identified, price, quality, fit, comfort, good customer service, fashion, and the opinions of others as the purchase determinants of consumers to purchase footwear. To influence the attitude of consumers, price and quality are found to be the important factors

Therefore, it is reviewed that the researches done previously to understand the response of consumers toward marketing activities focused on product, price, place, and promotion, demographic and psychological factors. But the researchers in this study have considered 4Ps (product, price, place, promotion). To measure customer's responsiveness

the researchers also consider another variable 'service'. Though it is not included in marketing mix, but service of any organization has a great effect to measure the attitude of consumers toward the marketing activities of super shops in Bangladesh.

3. Objectives of the study

The present study is aimed to analyze the responsiveness of consumers' toward marketing mix of Meena Bazaar.

Specific objectives of this study are as follows:

- To identify the responses of the consumers toward the product/service of Meena bazaar.
- To identify the responses of the consumers toward the price of products at Meena bazaar.
- To identify the responses of the consumers toward the location of Meena bazaar.
- To identify the feedback of the consumers toward the promotional activities of Meena bazaar.

3.1 Research question and hypothesis: Is there any relation between customer responsiveness and marketing activities of Meena Bazaar in Bangladesh?

To test the research question, following null and alternative hypothesis are designed.

Hypothesis 1:

Ho: There is no significant association between customer response and product of Meena Bazaar.

Ha: There is significant association between customer response and product of Meena Bazaar.

Hypothesis 2:

Ho: There is no significant association between customer response and price of products at Meena Bazaar.

Ha: There is significant association between customer response and price of products at Meena Bazaar.

Hypothesis 3:

Ho: There is no significant association between customer response and location of Meena Bazaar.

Ha: There is significant association between customer response and location of Meena Bazaar.

Hypothesis 4:

Ho: There is no significant association between customer response and promotion of Meena Bazaar.

Ha: There is significant association between customer response and promotion of Meena Bazaar.

Hypothesis 5:

Ho: There is no significant association between customer response and service of Meena Bazaar.

Ha: There is significant association between customer response and service of Meena Bazaar.

4. Research Methodology

The research is descriptive in nature. Data and information required for this study were collected from both primary and secondary sources. Primary source includes structured questionnaire and data were collected from different areas of Dhaka city. Secondary data were collected from company website, reports, electronic database and journals to develop theoretical background for the study. Variables covered in the study were selected based on the objectives of the study. The variables covered in the study are product, price, place and promotion and service. A total number of 11 different outlets of Meena Bazaar were selected and sample of 100 respondents were selected randomly. A total number of 150 structured questionnaires were delivered of which 100 respondents provided feedback. The survey was conducted in February 2012 in Dhaka city. Random sampling technique has been used to collect data. A structured questionnaire was developed by using nine-step likert scales ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The questionnaire consists of 19 statements that are able to explore the response of the consumer toward the marketing activities of Meena Bazaar accurately.

Data entry was done in SPSS 16.0 data editor and analyzed under some specific hypothesis. Statistical tools like frequency, crosstab and regression were used to assess and interpret data. To interpret the data, frequency and cross tabulation were used in the first phase. To test the hypotheses, multiple regressions were used as a statistical tool at 0.05 and significance level.

5. Analysis

5.1 Descriptive Analysis:

The frequency distribution of the considered variables is shown in Table 2.1 to 2.13(Appendix-A).

From the cross tab combining the number of visit weekly and the overall image rate in Table 3.1 (Appendix B), it is apparent that for every type of visitors the image is seemed to be positive. For the infrequent visitors (Once), frequent visitors (Twice or Thrice), and regular visitors (More than that), 83% claimed to have good and very good image toward meena bazaar. The proportion of visitors having extremely good image, though negligible, lies for the case of frequent and regular visitors.

From the cross tab combining the duration of shopping and the overall image rate in Table 3.2 (Appendix B), it is apparent that for every type of customer the image is seemed to be positive. For the customers, who are shopping from last three months, last 6 months, last one year, last 2 years and more than that, 66% claimed to have good and very good image toward Meena Bazaar. The percentage of customers having extremely good image are 33%. Among them, most of the customers are lying in the category of last 2 years and more than that.

Relationship between the factors which affect the response of the consumer and the overall image of Meena Bazaar:

Table 1: Relationship between product and the overall image of Meena Bazaar:

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.854 ^a	.729	.721	.388
a. Predictors: (Constant), Offer branded products, Variety products, Quality product				

From Table-1 it can be seen that there is slight difference between R-Square and Adjusted R-Square. It indicates that the addition of new independent variable as well as new samples would hardly affect the regression effect. The adjusted value of R-Square 0.721 describes that 72.1% variation in the dependent variable can be accounted for by the variation in the independent variables. It shows there is high significance of the variables, as the value of R is closer to 1; representing high dependence among the variables.

Table 2: Coefficients of Dependent and Independent variables:

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.864	.645		-2.890	.005
	Quality product	.586	.068	.536	8.627	.000
	Variety products	.355	.068	.309	5.226	.000
	Offer branded products	.266	.068	.235	3.893	.000
a. Dependent Variable: image rate						

Even the coefficients of the independent variables are significant to reject the null hypotheses for each variable. Thus, it can be said that product quality, variety products, and branded product have significant impact on overall satisfaction of consumers toward the image of Meena Bazar.

Table 3: Relationship between price and the overall image of Meena Bazaar

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.461 ^a	.213	.205	.654
a. Predictors: (Constant), High price				

Though the values of R-square and adjusted R-square is closer, the value of R (0.461) resides very negligible to estimate the dependence among the variables. The adjusted R-square of 0.205 dictates only 20% variation in the dependent variable to be accounted for by the variation in the independent variables. The addition of new variables or new samples would hardly strengthen the fact.

Table 4: Coefficients of Dependent and Independent variables:

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.039	.991		3.066	.003
	High price	.610	.119	.461	5.146	.000
a. Dependent Variable: image rate						

Regardless of reduced value of R and corresponding value of R-square and Adjusted R-square, the significance of high-price is satisfactory enough to reject the null hypothesis and establish the fact that Meena Bazar charges higher prices for the products they offer.

Table 5: Relationship between place and the overall image of Meena Bazaar

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.454 ^a	.206	.198	.657
a. Predictors: (Constant), Reasonable distance				

Though the values of R-square and Adjusted R-square is closer, the value of R (0.454) resides moderate to estimate the dependence among the variables. The adjusted R-square of 0.198 dictates only 19.80% variation in the dependent variable to be accounted for by the variation in the independent variables. The addition of new variables or new samples would hardly strengthen the fact.

Table 6: Coefficients of Dependent and Independent variables:

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.621	.896		4.043	.000
	Reasonable distance	.535	.106	.454	5.047	.000
a. Dependent Variable: image rate						

Regardless of reduced value of R and corresponding value of R-square and Adjusted R-square, the significance of reasonable distance is satisfactory enough to reject the null hypothesis and establish the fact that Meena Bazar is placed in a reasonable distance from the consumers' habitat.

Table 7: Relationship between promotion and the overall image of Meena Bazaar

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.840 ^a	.705	.690	.409
a. Predictors: (Constant), discount, Outlet birthday, Seasonal campaign, Special day offer, Supersaving offer				

From the table it can be seen that there is slight difference between R-Square and Adjusted R-Square. It indicates that the addition of new independent variable as well as new samples would hardly affect the regression effect. The adjusted value of R-Square 0.690 describes that 69% variation in the dependent variable can be accounted for by the variation in the independent variables. It shows there is high significance of the variables, as the value of R is closer to 1; representing high dependence among the variables.

Table 8: Coefficients of Dependent and Independent variables:

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.433	.652		-2.198	.030
	Outlet birthday	.201	.075	.206	2.671	.009
	Supersaving offer	.292	.070	.296	4.177	.000
	Special day offer	.247	.068	.248	3.634	.000
	Seasonal campaign	.192	.066	.194	2.896	.005
	Discount	.239	.066	.226	3.645	.000
a. Dependent Variable: image rate						

Even the coefficients of the independent variables are significant to reject the null hypotheses for each variable. Thus, it can be said that promotion on outlet birthday, super savings offer, special day offer, seasonal campaign and discount have significant impact on overall satisfaction of consumers toward the image of Meena Bazar.

Table 9: Relationship between service and the overall image of Meena Bazaar:

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.878 ^a	.770	.755	.363
a. Predictors: (Constant), Comfortable, Membership, Fast shopping, Specious , Friendly environment, neat and clean				

From the table it can be seen that there is slight difference between R-Square and Adjusted R-Square. It indicates that the addition of new independent variable as well as new samples would hardly affect the regression effect. The adjusted value of R-Square 0.755 describes that 75.5% variation in the dependent variable can be accounted for by the variation in the independent variables. It shows there is high significance of the variables, as the value of R is closer to 1; representing high dependence among the variables.

Table 10: Coefficients of Dependent and Independent variables:

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-3.755	.739		-5.083	.000
	Membership card	.210	.073	.174	2.878	.005
	Neat and clean	.490	.077	.428	6.384	.000
	Friendly environment	.133	.074	.113	1.787	.077
	Specious	.162	.071	.139	2.285	.025
	Fast shopping	.375	.072	.312	5.238	.000
	Comfortable	.059	.070	.050	.839	.404
a. Dependent Variable: image rate						

From the above table we can see that the significance level of membership (0.005), surroundings (0.000), specious crowded (0.025) and fast shopping (0.000) are below 0.05, which indicates that these variables have significant relationships with overall image of Meena Bazaar. On the other hand, friendly environment and comfort ability have significance level value more than 0.05, which indicates that these variables have no significant relationship with the image of Meena Bazaar.

Thus, it can be said that membership (sig .005), surroundings, specious crowded and fast shopping have significant impact on overall satisfaction of consumers toward the image of Meena Bazar. On the other hand, friendly environment and comfort ability don't have significant impact on overall satisfaction of consumers toward the image of Meena Bazar.

6. Findings

Out of total number 16 variables studied, 14 factors seem to be associated with overall image of Meena Bazaar. Among 05 considered hypotheses, for the first four the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, these variables have significant association with the response of the consumer about overall image of Meena Bazaar. In case of the fifth hypothesis, the significance of the variables (membership card, neat and clean, friendly environment, specious, fast shopping and comfortable) are 0.005, 0.000, 0.077, 0.025, 0.000 and 0.404 respectively. As the significance level of friendly environment and comfort ability is above the significance level (5%), this null hypothesis is not accepted. It is found that the response of the consumer about overall image of Meena Bazaar is not influenced by friendly environment and comfort ability. This analysis indicates that the response of the consumer about overall image of Meena Bazaar depends on product quality, product variety, branded products, high price, reasonable distance, outlet birthday, supersaving offer, special day offer, seasonal campaign, discount, membership card, neat and clean, specious and fast shopping.

7. Recommendations and Conclusion

In the growing field of superstores in Bangladesh, significant factors have been identified. Among them, the most important factors are firstly, the quality of products; secondly, prices offered by the super store authorities; thirdly, the distribution channels used by the super store and finally the promotional efforts. Meena bazaar is one of the potential parts in this sector. In the scenery of different findings, following recommendations can be made:

Majority of consumers believed that Meena Bazaar arrange a variety of products. But they should also try to collect some local rare food items, which the consumers can easily buy from *katcha bazaar* at a reasonable cost.

Consumers are satisfied with their current pricing. But a good number of people argued that they are charging high price. They can offer different quality products at different price so that the lower income people can afford.

Meena Bazaar has 13 outlets all over the country and most of them in Dhaka city. Only two are in Sylhet and Chittagong. They should try to open more outlets in different districts in Bangladesh.

The promotional effort of Meena Bazaar is satisfactory and it should be continued. Meena bazaar should try to initiate advertising through T.V and radio. Thus they can make a distinction offers from others. At the same time they should prepare creative advertisement that go in favor of all classes of people.

Consumers are satisfied with the atmosphere, services of employees and with the performance of the employees. A few number of people are not satisfied with these mentioned factors. Meena bazaar can train their personnel to make them more knowledgeable and interact well with the customers.

Meena Bazaar should try to adopt more and more societal marketing activities to build a specific image.

To hold and create new customers Meena Bazaar can follow some strategies:

- i. Gather information about customer needs on a regular basis.
- ii. Carry out marketing activities based on the current need about customers.
- iii. Make certain that the shop's activities enhance customer satisfaction.
- iv. Set prices by considering the affordability of all classes of people.

Meena Bazaar has a large market share among different super shops in our country. They are able to hold such a position by projecting a constructive image among the consumers. Meena bazaar is continuously improving through diversification in their marketing mix. If they are able to continue these, they can keep their customers satisfied for a long time.

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Appendix A

Frequencies along with percentage

Table 2.1: Frequency of visiting Meena Bazar in a week

Weekly visit		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Once	45	45.0	45.0
	Twice or Thrice	38	38.0	83.0
	More than that	17	17.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table 2.2: Frequency of mode of purchase

Purchase Term		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Cash	68	68.0	68.0
	credit card	32	32.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table 2.3: Frequency of time staying with Meena Bazaar

Duration of Shopping		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	last 3 months	29	29.0	29.0
	last 6 months	19	19.0	48.0
	Last 1 year	25	25.0	73.0
	last 2 years	12	12.0	85.0
	More than that	15	15.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table 2.4: Frequency of having membership card

Membership Card		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	31	31.0	31.0
	No	69	69.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table 2.5: Frequency of facilities receiving being a member

Membership facilities		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	high quality product	11	11.0	35.5
	price discount	13	13.0	77.4
	free gift	1	1.0	80.6
	up coming information	4	4.0	93.5
	Others	2	2.0	100.0
	Total	31	31.0	
Missing	System	69	69.0	
Total		100	100.0	

Table 2.6: Frequency of sources of information

First come to know.		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Family/Relatives	26	26.0	26.0
	Friends	29	29.0	55.0
	Co-workers	20	20.0	75.0
	Tv ad	1	1.0	76.0
	Newspaper ad	24	24.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table 2.7: Frequency of first reason to visit Meena Bazaar

First reason to visit.		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Recommendation from family	21	21.0	21.0
	Suggestion from friends & coworkers	16	16.0	37.0
	Advertisement	9	9.0	46.0
	Image	12	12.0	58.0
	Easy of shopping	25	25.0	83.0
	Sense of quality product	9	9.0	92.0
	Feeling of being higher social class	6	6.0	98.0
	Others	2	2.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table 2.8: Frequency of second reason to visit Meena Bazaar

Secod reason to visit.		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Recommendation from family	10	10.0	10.0
	Suggestion from friends & coworkers	9	9.0	19.0
	Advertisement	8	8.0	27.0
	Image	10	10.0	37.0
	Easy of shopping	24	24.0	61.0
	Sense of quality product	30	30.0	91.0
	Feeling of being higher social class	6	6.0	97.0
	Others	3	3.0	100.0

Table 2.9: Frequency of third reason to visit Meena Bazaar

Third reason to visit.		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Recommendation from family	11	11.0	11.0
	Suggestion from friends & coworkers	3	3.0	14.0
	Advertisement	5	5.0	19.0
	Image	23	23.0	42.0
	Easy of shopping	13	13.0	55.0
	Sense of quality product	18	18.0	73.0
	Feeling of being higher social class	26	26.0	99.0
	Others	1	1.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table 2.10: Frequency of first source to know about Meena Bazaar

First source to know about Meena Bazar		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Newspapers	41	41.0	41.0
	Banner	21	21.0	62.0
	Billboards	28	28.0	90.0
	Leaflets	8	8.0	98.0
	Insertions	2	2.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table 2.11: Frequency of second source to know about Meena Bazaar

Second source to know about Meena Bazar		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Newspapers	35	35.0	35.0
	Banner	26	26.0	61.0
	Billboards	22	22.0	83.0
	Leaflets	13	13.0	96.0
	Insertions	1	1.0	97.0
	Total	3	3.0	100.0
		100	100.0	

Table 2.12: Frequency of third source to know about Meena Bazaar

third source to know about Meena Bazar		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Newspaper	8	8.0	8.0
	Banner	15	15.0	23.0
	Billboards	8	8.0	31.0
	Leaflets	41	41.0	72.0
	Insertions	13	13.0	85.0
	Total	15	15.0	100.0
		100	100.0	

Table 2.13: Image rate of Meena Bazaar

Image of Meena Bazar		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	5	5.0	5.0
	Somewhat good	9	9.0	14.0
	Very good	49	49.0	63.0
	very good	34	34.0	97.0
	Extremely good	3	3.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Appendix B

Table- 3.1: Cross Tabulation between Number of visit*Image of Meena Bazar.

		Image of Meena Bazar					Total
		Neutral	Somewhat good	Good	Very good	Extremely good	
Visit	Once	2	4	23	16	0	45
	Twice or Thrice	2	3	17	14	2	38
	More than that	1	2	9	4	1	17
Total		5	9	49	34	3	100

Table- 3.2: Cross Tabulation between Duration of shopping*Image of Meena Bazar.

		Image of Meena Bazar				Total
		Somewhat good	Good	Very good	Extremely good	
Duration	Last 3 months	0	7	14	5	26
	Last 6 months	1	3	10	5	19
	Last 1 year	0	8	12	5	25
	Last 2 years	0	0	3	9	12
	More than that	0	0	9	9	18
Total		1	18	48	33	100